

THE EFFECTS OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON THE MECHANICAL

PROPERTIES OF ALUMINUM-GRAPHITE COMPOSITES*

William C. Harrigan, Jr., and David M. Goddard
Materials Sciences Laboratory
The Aerospace Corporation
El Segundo, California 90245

Aluminum-graphite composites are produced through molten infiltration of aluminum into continuous tows of graphite fibers by means of a process developed by The Aerospace Corporation. This process produces a continuous rod of composite that is subsequently fabricated into larger structures. This fabrication step involves hot-pressing of the wires in temperature ranges where the matrix is fully solid, fully liquid, or partially liquid and solid. The influence of the temperature region of fabrication on the final mechanical properties is discussed. The effects of cleaning of the precursor rod on the bonding of this composite are demonstrated. Fracture analysis with scanning electron microscopy is used to demonstrate the role of pressing parameters on the fracture process and the resulting mechanical properties.

* This paper reflects research supported by the U.S. Air Force under Space and Missile Systems Organization (SAMSO) Contract No. FO4701-74-C-0075.

Introduction

For several years, The Aerospace Corporation has produced aluminum-graphite composites through molten infiltration of aluminum into continuous tows of graphite fibers. Typically, this composite is in the form of rods or wire ~1.3 mm in diameter. These wires can be consolidated into structural shapes through various processes, including diffusion bonding, liquid-phase hot-pressing, sintering, or brazing.

The most successful consolidation technique developed thus far has been partial liquid-phase hot-pressing, in which wires are bonded under pressure at temperatures above the solidus point, in the two-phase solid-liquid state. Extensive studies have been conducted at The Aerospace Corporation¹ and elsewhere² to optimize the temperature, pressure, and time parameters for the consolidation technique.

An extensive compilation of the mechanical properties of aluminum-graphite fiber composites has recently been prepared that reports on the properties obtained with optimum parameters.³ This report will concentrate on the effects of nonoptimum parameters on the mechanical properties as well as presenting methods for improving the consolidation techniques in the near future. It is presented in four sections: the effects of pressing temperature, the effects of initial fiber content, the effects of cleaning techniques, and the near-term improvements that can be made.

The Effects of Pressing Temperature

Composites have been produced with the following aluminum matrices: 1100, A413, 356, 6061, 201, and 202. The 1100 Al and A413 have single melting temperatures. Consolidation of composite wires made from these alloys without the aid of braze foils has been unsuccessful to date. The remaining alloys have melt ranges, and consolidation of composite wires with these matrices has been successful in the temperature range between the solidus and liquidus points for each alloy. Many experiments at The Aerospace Corporation indicate that the fiber volume fraction of a consolidated bar depends on the initial wire fiber content and the consolidation temperature for a given alloy. The fiber fraction is independent of pressure from 3.5 to 35 MPa.⁴

This behavior can be demonstrated with the 6061 Al-Thornel 50 composite system. The matrix has a melt range of 584 to 649°C. The initial composite wire contains ~30 vol% fiber. Bars that are pressed at 630°C contain 45 vol% fiber, and bars pressed at 615°C contain 31 vol% fiber. This behavior is consistent with the fact that more liquid phase is present at the higher temperature and can be expelled during pressing. The higher-temperature pressing

technique has several shortcomings, however. Among them are the higher level of aluminum carbide formed during pressing (1600 ppm at 630°C compared with 625 ppm at 615°C) and increased fiber-fiber contact (Fig. 1). The second phase in the aluminum in these micrographs is not carbide; rather it is the aluminum-silicon eutectic that is present in the matrix. A further demonstration of fiber degradation caused by high melt pressing is the relatively low tensile strength of the bars. The extent of this is demonstrated in Table I. Bars pressed at 615°C have an average tensile strength of 558 MPa with a fiber content of 31 vol%. Bars pressed at 630°C have an average tensile strength of 560 MPa with the higher fiber content of 45 vol%. With the higher fiber content, the bars pressed at 630°C should be 1.5 times the strength of those pressed at 615°C. A possible explanation for the decrease in fiber strength is fiber breakage during pressing; however, there is a very minor amount of fiber breakage caused by these pressing procedures. This breakage is monitored by dissolving the matrix during the aluminum carbide analysis.

This lack of strength increase with fiber fraction increase is not caused by exposure of the composite to the temperature cycle alone. This was demonstrated at The Aerospace Corporation⁴ and elsewhere.⁵ The experiments involved taking 30-cm sections of wire, breaking them in half, and identifying each half. One piece was heated to 645°C for 10 min to simulate the heat cycle of consolidation. Both pieces of the wire were then tensile-tested and analyzed for aluminum carbide. In all cases, the tensile strengths of the wires were identical, and a slight increase in aluminum carbide of 100 ppm was found.

The effects of temperature appear to be related to a competition between strengthening by increased fiber contents attainable at higher temperatures and weakening by chemical interactions between the aluminum and the graphite at high temperatures. This chemical interaction is aggravated when large quantities of liquid are expelled during hot-pressing. This is probably a result of a washing action of the liquid during expulsion. Satisfactory mechanical properties of consolidated composites have been obtained when pressing is carried out at a temperature between the solidus point and halfway between the solidus and liquidus points. Incomplete bonding results when the wire is consolidated at a temperature below the solidus point for the matrix.

Table I. Strength of 6061 Al-Thornel 50 Bars

Pressing Temperature, C	Fiber Content, vol%	No. of Bars	Tensile Strength, MPa			Al ₄ C ₃ , ppm
			High	Low	Average	
630	45 ± 4	10	728	379	560	1600
615	31 ± 3	20	678	496	558	625

The Effects of Initial Fiber Content

Precursor wire is being produced by two companies that use basically the same method for fiber protection prior to liquid metal infiltration: The Aerospace Corporation and Fiber Materials, Inc. Slight differences in manufacturing techniques cause a difference in fiber content of the wire. The wire produced by FMI contains ~24 vol% fiber in the 201 Al-Thornel 50 system. The wire produced by Aerospace with the same system contains ~28.5 vol% fiber. This difference in fiber content is reflected in the tensile strength of the wire: FMI wire has a strength of 606 MPa, and Aerospace wire has a strength of 690 MPa. When these values are compared on the basis of fiber property utilization, both wires are equal. This can be shown by plotting tensile strength as a function of fiber content (Fig. 2). A rule-of-mixtures area is defined on this figure because the fiber tensile strength is variable, 2080 ± 407 MPa. The shaded areas show the properties of the wire at the upper portion of this rule-of-mixtures area.

Plates and bars were produced by consolidation of the precursor. Identical parameters were used for each wire group. Parameters used for bars differ from those used for plates. Tensile strengths and corresponding fiber contents for these consolidated samples are shown as open and closed symbols in Fig. 2. At least four samples were cut from each plate. The average, high, and low tensile strength values are indicated. In general, consolidation into bars increases the fiber volume fraction of the composite and shifts the tensile strength to the low region of the rule-of-mixtures area. Consolidation of plates requires the addition of foils for proper alignment of fibers. The plates have a slightly lower fiber content than the bars and corresponding lower tensile strength. In Fig. 2, it can be seen that a straight line representing the tensile strength of all bars and plates as a function of fiber content corresponds to the lower bound of the rule-of-mixtures area. This demonstrates that graphite fibers can be used efficiently at higher fiber contents if they are incorporated into the aluminum matrix properly.

The Effects of Cleaning

After the molten infiltration process is completed, the hot wire is exposed to a complex, impure atmosphere. An adherent reaction product is formed on the surface of the wire during this operation. The first attempt at removing this surface layer was to glass-bead the wires before pressing. This process did result in a clean surface, and well-bonded bars were produced with, however, low tensile strength and modulus. Tensile tests on cleaned and uncleaned wire showed that fiber damage during the cleaning reduced the tensile strength from 690 to 414 MPa. Consolidation of this damaged wire resulted in bars with tensile strengths of 299 MPa and

moduli of 120 GPa (Table II). When this damaging cleaning procedure was discontinued and bars were pressed with noncleaned wire, modest gains were made in strengths, from 299 to 345 MPa. Spectacular gains were made in moduli, which doubled from 120 to 240 GPa. The moduli were those predicted by the rule of mixtures.

Table II. Cleaning Methods for Aluminum-Graphite Composite Wire

Composite System	Cleaning Method	Tensile Strength, MPa	Modulus, GPa	Fiber Content, vol%
356 Al-Thornel 50	Glass-bead	299	120	45
356 Al-Thornel 50	None	345	240	45
6061 Al-Thornel 50	None	415	144	27.5
6061 Al-Thornel 50	Chromic-phosphoric	578	157	28.9
201 Al-Thornel 50	None	565	160	27.0
201 Al-Thornel 50	Chromic-phosphoric	635	161	27.3

Bars pressed from the uncleaned wire had a bond line between prior wires. In some cases, this bond line was broken up in places; however, these bond lines could be traced throughout the bar (Fig. 3). This incomplete bonding leads to the wires breaking individually in the bar. Evidence of this is seen in scanning electron micrographs of bar fractures. Low-magnification micrographs show evidence of fracture steps corresponding to prior wires (Fig. 4). Higher magnification micrographs show areas where the wires pulled apart because of the poor bonding (Fig. 5).

After many cleaning procedures were tried, satisfactory bonding was achieved when the wire was immersed for ~1 min in a dilute chromic-phosphoric acid solution that was heated to 90°C (100 ml H₃PO₄, 100 g CrO₃ and 1 liter H₂O). This cleaner is rinsed off with tap water, and the wire is dried immediately. The wire appears brighter after this cleaning operation.

The success of the cleaning operation is emphasized by the fracture surfaces of two bars seen in Fig. 6. The upper bar is a 6061 Al-Thornel 50 composite that was consolidated with cleaned wires. This bar had a tensile strength of 578 MPa and a modulus of 157 GPa. The lower bar is an identical composite that was consolidated with wire produced at the same time as the previous bar but which was not cleaned. This bar had a tensile strength of

415 MPa and a modulus of 144 GPa. The fracture surface of the lower bar appears to be prior wire surfaces that never bonded.

The chromic-phosphoric cleaning solution has been used successfully on 1100, 6061, 201, 202, and 5052 aluminum matrix composites. Another cleaner has also been used on the 1100 and 6061 matrix composites: a standard titanium cleaner, 50% HNO_3 in water with 2% HF, which is used at room temperature. When this solution is used on the 201 or 202 matrix wires, however, the surface of the wires turns black. Concentrated HNO_3 causes a surface reaction, but the surface is not bright after the cleaning. The best results so far have been with the chromic-phosphoric solution.

Near-Term Improvements

In the section on the effects of initial fiber content, a point is made that the bar strength properties increase with increasing fiber content from 25 to 35 vol%. This strength increase can only be accomplished by increasing the fiber content of the precursor wire. Bar properties can be increased during fabrication by increasing fiber content ~5% during consolidation. Any further increase in fiber fraction is accompanied by increased fiber-matrix interaction and a decrease in strength. Therefore, precursor wire with 25 vol% fiber can be consolidated into bars with between 25 and 30 vol% fiber, and these bars will exhibit an increasing strength over this range. Conveniently, wire with 29 vol% fiber is also available; this wire can be consolidated into bars with increasing strengths as the fiber content is raised from 29 to ~35 vol% fiber. The next major improvement in performance of the composite will come when precursor wire with ≥ 35 vol% fiber becomes available.

The aluminum-graphite composites described in this paper have been produced with 8-ended tows of Thornel 50 graphite fibers. The aluminum and graphite fibers are very unevenly distributed in the wire (Fig. 7). There are large areas of aluminum without fibers throughout the wire. The eight strands that were combined in the tows have not been dispersed, and, in several cases, the two 720-filament groups that were combined to make the 1440-fiber strand of Thornel 50 are also visible. It seems reasonable, then, that production of composites with 4-ended tows should result in a composite with higher fiber content because of the elimination of interbundle aluminum areas.

A further advantage of the smaller-diameter wire is that it would require less total deformation of the wires to achieve complete consolidation. The composite strength degradation that has been observed after high melt pressing may be only partially caused by large amounts of liquid expulsion during pressing; it may also be caused by the wire deformation during pressing. When the 8-stranded Thornel 50-aluminum composites are consolidated to give

optimum properties, the 1.3-mm-diam wires are pressed into layers with an effective thickness of 0.9 mm. In order to determine the effect of the deformation on the strength of the composite, a pressing experiment was conducted at The Aerospace Corporation.⁴ This experiment involved pressing individual wires from their initial 1.3-mm diam to an oval with a short dimension of 0.9 mm. Tensile tests were conducted on the pressed wire. The strength of the initial wire was ~725 MPa, and the strength of the deformed wire was ~620 MPa. The latter is approximately the strength of the bars after consolidation, which suggests that the bars with a tensile strength of 620 MPa are well bonded and reflect the true strength of the composite after hot deformation.

Another phenomenon that must be investigated is the segregation of the graphite to the eutectic regions of alloys that contain such a phase. Examples of this are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. When these composites are pressed in the solid-liquid region of the phase diagram, the fibers are exposed to the liquid phase throughout the pressing cycle. This liquid padding may be a reason why the 6061, 201, and 202 matrix composites can be successfully consolidated. However, an effort must be made to determine if this liquid in contact with the fiber is detrimental to the strength of the composite. Also, when the liquid phase in contact with the fiber freezes, voids are formed because of the volume change during the phase change. It appears that the voids formed during freezing contribute to poor transverse properties of the composite. Areas on a transverse fracture that appear to be void surfaces created during freezing are shown in Fig. 10. The role of this eutectic phase appears to be very important in determining the mechanical behavior of this composite and has received little attention to date.

It appears that large improvements can be made in the mechanical properties of aluminum-graphite composites by: (1) optimizing the distribution of fibers in the matrix by decreasing the number of strands per tow, (2) decreasing the initial wire diameter to decrease composite deformation during consolidation, and (3) understanding the role of the eutectic phase in determining the matrix-fiber bond.

References

1. Harrigan, W. C., Jr.: Fabrication of Aluminum-Graphite Composite, Technical Report No. TR-0075(9250-03)-2, The Aerospace Corp., El Segundo, Calif. [1974]
2. Pepper, R. T., and Penty, R. A.: "Mechanical Properties of Aluminum-Graphite Composites Prepared by Liquid Phase Hot Pressing," J. Composite Mater. [January, 1974] Vol. 8, 29-37

3. Amateau, M. F., Harrigan, W. C., Jr., and Kendall, E. G.: Mechanical Properties of Aluminum Alloy-Graphite Fiber Composites, Technical Report No. TR-0075(9250-03)-3, The Aerospace Corp., El Segundo, Calif. [1975]
4. Harrigan, W. C., Jr., and Hudson, S. P.: unpublished research, The Aerospace Corp., El Segundo, Calif. [1974]
5. Pepper, R. T., Penty, R. A., and Allen, S. J.: Fabrication of Aluminum-Graphite Composites, Technical Report No. AMMRC CTR 73-25, Army Materials and Mechanics Research Center, Watertown, Mass. [July, 1973]

[Note: Figure 1 appears on succeeding page for editorial reasons.]

2. Tensile strength of 201 Al-Thornel 50 composite for various volume fractions of fiber and processing treatments.

1. Optical micrograph of bars of 6061 Al-Thornel 50 composite pressed at (a) 630°C and (b) 615°C.

3. Optical micrograph of bond line between wires in a 6061 Al-Thornel 50 composite (fiber diameter = $6\ \mu\text{m}$).

4. Low-magnification scanning electron micrograph of poorly bonded 201 Al-Thornel 50 composite. Shear-out of original wires is evident on either end.

5. Scanning electron micrograph of fracture of 201 Al-Thornel 50 composite near original wire-wire interface. Large cavity indicates lack of bonding of the wires (fiber diameter = $6\ \mu\text{m}$).

6. Fractograph of two tensile bars of 6061 Al-Thornel 50 composite. The upper bar was produced with wires that were cleaned while the lower bar was produced with uncleaned wire.

7. Scanning electron micrograph of polished end of 201 Al-Thornel 50 composite.

8. Optical micrograph of 356 Al-Thornel 50 composite wire. All fibers are segregated to aluminum-silicon eutectic regions (fiber diameter = $6\ \mu\text{m}$).

9. Scanning electron micrograph of polished end of 202 Al-Thornel 50 composite wire. Fibers are localized in copper-aluminum eutectic regions (fiber diameter = $6\ \mu\text{m}$).

10. Scanning electron micrographs of transverse fracture of 201 Al-Thornel 50 composite: (b) is a higher magnification of the center of the area shown in (a). The shiny rounded areas appear to be remnants of freezing volume change (fiber diameter = $6\ \mu\text{m}$).

DISCUSSION/Session 6

The following questions were addressed to J.D. Ray, Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories, Wright-patterson Air Force Base, Ohio

QUESTION: J.H. Underwood, U.S. Army Benet Weapons Lab

Please comment on the relative tooling costs of composite versus metal components.

ANSWER:

In general the tooling cost for composite components are significantly lower because of reduced piece-part count for the component, therefore requiring only a fraction of the tools for the comparable metal component.

QUESTION: J.H. Underwood

Have you seen any fracture problems around the cutouts you described in the highly loaded spars in aircraft components?

ANSWER:

At the present state of analysis capability and design sophistication, stress concentrations associated with holes, cutouts, etc. are handled with relative ease.

QUESTION: W. Bishop, Ciba-Geigy (UK), Duxford, Cambridge

I would like to ask the speaker how severe he anticipates the environmental problems to be in real-time exposure. Will the problem be more severe than the old established structural adhesive experience? Even in the adhesive field efforts to correlate accelerated exposure with real-time exposure have proved difficult. Further, the adhesive joints are currently worked at low stress levels in comparison to the ultimate strength of the material. Would the speaker please comment.

ANSWER:

Although a significant amount of data for environmental effects on composites does not yet exist I do not believe the problem to be severe. Data in the form of wet design allowables, fatigue and etc. where the specimens and components are conditioned to worse cases, i.e. saturated conditions and tested at worse conditions, i.e. saturated and at the expected use temperature of the material, indications are that the environmental effects can be handled satisfactorily. With the current data base and experience I would refer to the environmental effects as a design consideration rather than a problem. This is not to say that all the solutions are in hand. The question of correlative laboratory procedures to accurately predict the effect of the environment on the life of a structure from accelerated tests still remains.

QUESTION: R.G. Schliekelmann, Holland

Did you test to destruction advanced composite articles after several years of flight operation? If so, how did the outcome compare with a similar article with zero flight hours?

ANSWER:

No, not as yet, but plans to perform such a test have been made. However, in the laboratory we have measured the residual strength of large components after long-time fatigue and found little or no degradation as yet. But the data base is rather small so I hesitate to conclude that composites do not wear out.

The following questions and comments were addressed to F.M.H. Carpay, Battelle/Geneva.

QUESTION: R. Naslain, Bordeaux University, Talence, France

What kind of properties do you expect from the composites that you have described (for example: $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ or $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$)? In what fields do you situate their potential applications?

ANSWER:

There are no potential applications in the composites in the systems from vitreous state I have showed. In fact, I wanted to show that the technique works; the applications should be found in other systems.

QUESTION: G. Manfre, Technion S.p.a., Milano

1. When you quench very fast an article, the quenching rate varies through the cross section of the article, especially for thick ones. This may introduce inhomogeneities between the surface and the core of the material. How do these inhomogeneities affect the vitreous state of your materials?

2. In some of your materials the ratio between the diameter of the fibre and its length is very small, and so I wonder whether this is not under the necessary critical aspect ratio in order to get a re-inforcement?

ANSWER:

The answer to your first question is very difficult, as, in fact, we worked only with very small specimens. In the easily vitrifying materials, the specimens were of a length of some few centimeters and a diameter of 0.5 cm. The splat-cooled samples were thinner than half a centimeter. Therefore, we did not notice the inhomogeneities you mention. But I believe that in the case of large quantities this really may become a problem.

To answer your second question, I can say that the ratio is not more than 7.4 or 7.5. This means below the critical value.

QUESTION: P.M.B. Slate, Atomic Weapons Research Estab., England

How important would be the experimental temperature variations in the sample on the microstructure of composite made from the solid (glassy) state?

ANSWER:

Temperature variation will in general have two different microstructural effects: a) nucleation of new lamellae, pinching off of existing ones or thickness changes (e.g. "banding" phenomenon in off-eutectic solidification); b) change of period λ through a change of growth rate R .

As far as effect a) is concerned: we have not found any banding phenomenon in glassy state decompositions, nor in other solid state reactions. Nucleation ahead of the front in eutectoid decompositions caused by strong temperature fluctuation has happened.

Effect b): in eutectoid decompositions the effect is small because of the λ 4R-relationship; in glassy state decompositions we expect more influence on the experiments reported; however, some decompositions showed a much less pronounced dependence of λ on R.

COMMENT: G. Piatti, EURATOM CCR, Italy

I want to present some results obtained at the Materials Division - Euratom Research Center of Ispra (Italy) in collaboration with Laboratory C.I.S.E. - Milano (Italy), which confirm the conclusions of Dr. Carpay. We investigated the eutectic Ni-Ni₃Ta prepared from pure elements using the technique of unidirectional solidification.

This system is composed of Ni-Ta solution as matrix and intermetallic Ni₃Ta as second phase (Fig. 1). The structure shows two types of lamellae, namely primary coarse lamellae obtained from liquid phase at eutectic temperature and secondary fine lamellae obtained by unidirectional precipitation of Ni₃Ta from the solid solution due to the large variation of solubility of Ta with temperature (Fig. 2). It can be observed in agreement with the results of Dr. Carpay that under the same experimental condition, the inter-phase distance in the case of lamellae grown from solid state are smaller by a factor of about 20.

REPLY: Dr. Carpay

Your comment is very interesting, especially in comparison with the Co-Si system. Two special characteristics strike me:

1. I wonder why you find lamellae in the eutectic case, because the eutectic composition is very far to the Ni-side.
2. In this case the discontinuous reaction products are much better aligned than in my Co-Si case. This is due to the fact that the matrix lamellae, which show the precipitation, are much thicker. Therefore as well the eutectic as the precipitation can be aligned in one single process.

The following questions were addressed to P.M.B. Slate, Atomic Weapons Research Establishment, England.

QUESTION: P.C. Chou, Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania

Due to shock strength attenuation, there must be a limitation on the thickness of the specimens. What is the maximum thickness you have formed with this method?

Is there any possibility of using this technique for non-metal fibre and matrix?

ANSWER:

Although the shock wave attenuates, it starts off as a generally flat topped pulse of about 2 mm width. Traversing a solid medium the rarefaction would catch up with the head of the pulse after a distance of about 8 mm. However, the medium in this case is alternate solid and void so that attenuation is large. In practice, successful compaction occurs up to approximately 6 mm thickness of sample.

Several attempts were made to make aluminium composites explosively using 0.1 mm boron fibres on a tungsten core. Although bonding took place, the fibres tended to crack radially. This was attributed partly to the brittleness of the boron and partly due to the internal stresses set up when the shock wave reflected from the impedance mismatch of the boron/tungsten interface.

QUESTION: M. Blank, DFVLR, West Germany

During the report of Mr. Slate's paper, a micrograph has shown a very regular arrangement of pores at the interface boundaries.

What does Mr. Slate think about the influence of pores on the transverse shear strength of the composites?

ANSWER:

The regular arrangements of defects which Mr. Blank refers to in Fig. 5 have not definitely been shown to be due to porosity. For example, they are not evident in the unetched structure; they occur in aluminium but not in copper matrices. It could be that they are due to microporosity arising from the Monroe jet effect at the welding of the layers of foil. The effect can be minimized by adjusting the explosive pressure to a slightly lower value. This is partly demonstrated by comparing Fig. 7 with Fig. 8 in which complete compaction was deliberately avoided in order to hopefully reveal the mechanisms of welding.

Regarding the effect on mechanical properties, we have not tested in shear, but have tested in a direction parallel to the fibres when it was shown to have a strength equal to a similar composite formed by diffusion bonding and cross rolling.

QUESTION: J. Müller, Aero Consultants, DeBendorf, Switzerland

I do not see the advantage of steel ribbon reinforced epoxy type compared to the pipe of steel only, since one cannot improve on the specific strength of steel. Is it cheaper to produce?

ANSWER: J. Rexer, Battelle/Geneva Research Center, Switzerland

It is correct that the specific strength (strength/density) of our steel ribbon-reinforced epoxy composite is not higher than that of pure steel. The advantages, however, are different and can be shortly summarized as:

- cheaper material price because we are working with thin sheets which will be definitely cheaper on a price/strength basis than thick walled steel pipes.
- cheaper in fabrication because of the possibility of continuous fabrication (less joints, welds)
- steel pipes of such high strengths cannot be made in such a variety of dimensions
- the steel strip is of higher quality than steel pipes of similar strength hence leading to a high quality pipe product
- the corrosion resistance is already built into the composite material
- higher fracture toughness, thus more security against catastrophic failure
- more flexible structures are possible which is extremely important in off-shore risers and pipelines

QUESTION: Dr. Naslain, University of Bordeaux, Talence, France

Dr. Toth, did you find any relationship between the fibre-matrix interaction layer thickness and the mechanical properties in your boron-titanium composites?

ANSWER: I.J. Toth, TRW, Inc., Cleveland, Ohio

A critical interaction layer thickness of about 8000 \AA , obtained when using a fabrication cycle of 30 minutes at 1500°F , was found to give the optimum longitudinal ($184 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$) and transverse ($67 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$) room temperature strength.

QUESTION: W. Bishop, Ciba-Geigy (UK), Duxford, Cambridge

To what extent will the winding techniques (wet and prepreg winding) be incorporated in the future B/C(?) projects? Do AFML have any indication from long-term structural studies? I would guess that the potential would be limited since practical structures have cut-outs, discontinuity problems, changes of section, etc.

ANSWER: B.H. JONES, Goldsworthy, Torrance, California

The potential for filament winding aircraft structures is indeed limited by the problems of ensuring adequacy of design in the regions of cut outs, etc. The only application I am aware of that is undergoing active development relates to the filament winding of tail-booms for advanced rotor craft. In a more general context, interest is still being maintained in filament wound lattice structures for aerospace use.

QUESTION: M.J. Owen, University of Nottingham

Can you give me some feel for the relative investments in advanced handling equipment inside and outside the aero-space industry?

ANSWER: B.H. Jones

Confining attention to equipment for actually laying down the filamentary reinforcements, and excluding such items as autoclaves, my estimate for the aerospace industry would be \$8 million for tape laying equipment and associated developments, \$0.5 million for pultrusion and at least \$15 million for filament winding machines of various types. Outside the aerospace industry, tape-laying in the context discussed in my paper is not utilized and so no level of investment exists. In the USA, it is likely that approximately \$2 - \$5 million has been spent on various types of pultrusion machines and \$10 million on a myriad of filament winding machines. Added to these figures is a far more substantial sum for special purpose machines and processing equipment.

COMMENT: M. Salkind, AVCO, Lowell, Massachusetts

(re: Dr. Jones' paper) Vacuum injection molding of cloth is an economically attractive fabrication technique which has received little attention but which, I believe, will become significant in the future.

QUESTION: D. Stockel, G. Rau, Pforzheim, West Germany

1. Is the distribution of the steel short fibres good enough to guarantee a uniform electrical resistivity over the total length of the wire? From this point of view, I think it is better to use materials with continuous fibre, which can also be produced by similar methods.

2. Do you think there is an economic commercial use of steel fibre reinforced copper as an electrical conductor compared with age hardenable copper alloys?

ANSWER: Z. Hara, University of Tokyo

1. The distribution of the steel fibres was not so good. The shorter and finer fibres will be necessary to get uniform distribution.
2. If finer and stronger fibres could be available, this process would find commercial application. We used the steel fibre as an example of short fibre material to be well aligned in FRM and didn't consider direct application of it.

COMMENT: F. Carpay, Philips Research Laboratories, Eindhoven

(re: Z. Hara's and N. Fujimori's paper) Just a minor comment: If you think of your technique to obtain strong wires for electrical conduction, you may also think of a solid state reaction. The Cu-CuAl eutectoid gives a lamellar product with a tensile strength of 135 kg/mm^2 (however at small growth rates).

QUESTION: E. Murphy

What is the possible size of your Graphite Aluminum wires?

ANSWER: W.C. Harrigan, The Aerospace Corp., El Segundo, Cal.

Wire size is dependent upon the graphite precursor. Wires up to 600 feet long have been fabricated. The diameter of the wire is associated with the graphite fiber form. Eight ended Thornel 50 yields 0.6 to 1.0 mm diameter wires. PAN Fibers lead to wire diameters from 1 - 4 mm diameter.

The following questions were addressed to S. Dastin, Grumman Aerospace Corp., Bethpage, N.Y.

QUESTION: L. Michelove, Itek, Lexington, Massachusetts

How much of the cost of the part was attributed to quality control?

ANSWER:

12 to 15% in true production operation.

QUESTION: E. Scala, Ithaca, N.Y.

How do you control resin quality and reproducibility?

ANSWER:

- 1) Determination of chemical composition of resin.

- 2) Control of physical properties such as flow, tack get time, etc., of the prepreg.
- 3) Verification by physical testing of composites made from prepreg.
- 4) Testing coupon made during component fabrication.

QUESTION: E. Scala

Are there any examples of resin rejection?

ANSWER:

Grumman has used 35,000 lbs and rejected 200 to 300 pounds.

QUESTION: E. Scala

Are there any tests for properties as a function of time (aging effects)?

ANSWER:

There were no satisfactory short-time tests which would predict long-term degradation.

QUESTION: A. Shames, Rockwell International

Our experience has been that in curing graphite/epoxy to aluminum core a substantial reduction in properties occurs. Does your experience verify this and do you favor using co-curing if you can accept the lower properties?

ANSWER:

Grumman has used co-curing techniques for several years with no serious problems. There is some degradation (about 25 percent) for when bonding faces on a core. However, for good results, the faces must be kept flat during the co-cure.

QUESTION: (no name available)

What are operational component properties after several year's service life?

ANSWER:

McDonnell Douglas has found that the properties of Composite F-4 rudders are essentially unchanged after one and a half year's service.

QUESTION: (no name available)

What are the relative tooling costs of composites versus metals?

ANSWER:

Relative costs are difficult to evaluate since design for equivalent function performance is different. Overall tooling costs for composites are lower in properly selected cases.

QUESTION: A. Shames

Recent published work shows that polysulfide sealants are more permeable to moisture by a factor of 10 than certain organic finishes. What has been your experience on moisture entry and subsequent material deterioration?

ANSWER:

Moisture degradation is still a problem and is a major reason why low unit loading is still used.

QUESTION: H. Paruz, Israel

It is apparent that the extent of future applications of composites will depend upon reliable non-destructive testing. What are the new techniques being worked on and the general state of the art?

ANSWER:

It is believed that see through ultrasonic testing can be used for quality control testing and it is now being used. Biggest problem is the weak but not disbonded joint. Grumman is trying ultrasonic, infrared and holography techniques to try to locate weak bonds.

QUESTION: J.D. Buckley, NASA, Langley Hampton, Va.

How does one observe the deterioration of a plastic matrix material on an airplane that is seeing daily flight service? Can you NDT or detect mechanical failure of plastic matrix airplane structures on an aircraft in service?

ANSWER:

At present only techniques are visual examination. Better techniques are needed.

The following questions were addressed to J. Christian, General Dynamics, San Diego, California.

QUESTION: I.J. Toth, TRW Inc.

Is there a wall thickness limitation on B-Al tube fabrication? What

is the preferred starting material (tape) for tube fabrication?

ANSWER:

Tubes have been made with wall thicknesses of 0.160 inch and thicker walls are being considered. Plasma sprayed tape originally was used for tube, but fully consolidated monolayer is now used. Green and dry woven tapes are being considered.

QUESTION: W. Hoover

What is the orientation of the filaments in the tubes?

ANSWER:

All production tubes are uniaxial. Experimental tubes have been made with \pm 45 degree lay up.

QUESTION: B.R. Noton, Battelle Columbus Laboratories, Columbus, Ohio

The fatigue and compressive properties and fire resistance of boron aluminum appear attractive for high aspect-ratio wings of future civil aircraft designed to conserve fuel. Mr. Christian showed several structures similar to that required for box-beams of civil aircraft. Is there any work underway on such applications?

ANSWER:

The B-1 and YF-16 are the only aircraft now being considered.

QUESTION: I.J. Toth

Can you comment on machining of B-Al in terms of material removal mechanism?

ANSWER:

Cutting and shaping are much easier than anticipated when diamond cutting tools are used.

QUESTION: I.J. Toth

In the B-Al wing box you built and evaluated for the Navy, did you evaluate the corrosion behavior at the aluminum-steel interface area?

ANSWER:

No. The usual sealants were used at the joint and we experienced no problems.

QUESTION: K.K. Chawla, Inst. Mil de Eng., Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Don't you run into problems with interfacial reaction between B and Al? Above what temperature do you need a protective coating?

ANSWER:

No evidence for significant reaction for long-term exposure at temperatures up to 600°F. In general, B-Al are compatible at temperatures up to 950°F for short periods (few hours).

QUESTION: I.J. Toth

In clad forming of B-Al shapes, how do you control the residual stress situation (distortion), especially after the steel cladding is removed?

ANSWER:

There is spring back when the steel cladding is removed, but it is predictable and can be allowed for.

QUESTION: A. Shames, Rockwell International

What are the relative economic values of composite structures compared to conventional metal structures?

ANSWER:

Primary material costs of boron aluminum have decreased in the last few years. The semi-conventional metal fabrication techniques which can be used with B-Al also lead to lower fabrication costs. B-Al is now competitive with Ti for many structures, and in a few cases with Al Structures. Finished hardware is now available at under \$500 per pound.

QUESTION: R. Natarajan, Lord Corp., Erie, Pa.

(re: paper by Z. Hara and N. Fujimori) There was mention of the use of metallic powders. Has anyone used conventional powder metallurgical techniques for the fabrication of fiber reinforced metal matrix composites? What type of properties does one expect if the procedure is used?

ANSWER: J. Christian

Powder metallurgical techniques were tried for fabricating continuous filament reinforced metal matrix composites. The technique was not competitive with fabrication techniques now used.

Discussion by A. BERGHEZAN of the paper presented by G. S. DOBLE and I. J. TOTH, entitled : "ROLL DIFFUSION BONDING OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES", Session VI (Geneva and Boston)

The roll-diffusion bonding appears to emerge, besides extrusion, swaging and/or explosive bonding, as a most interesting method for the fabrication of metal matrix composite materials. It possesses some unique advantages : it is a high speed processing method and uses the existing techniques of large plant productions, which is likely to be a low-cost fabrication method. The authors should be congratulated for having demonstrated that sophistication is not necessarily associated with the fabrication of composite materials.

I would like to bring here a further confirmation that the method of roll-bonding works in many other combinations of components, as we have demonstrated in Brussels at the Union Carbide Research Labs, some years ago (1, 2, 3, 4).

By roll-bonding, we prepared several mono and multilayer tapes or sandwiches of the following materials : stainless steel wires in aluminium, (Fig. 1), interlieved plain carbon steel and aluminium foils or interlieved pre-aluminized steel and aluminium foils (Fig. 2 and 3), as well as composites consisting of alternate layers of a Co-30 Ni-1,2 Be alloy and aluminium (Fig. 4). In all these materials the bonding showed to be excellent.

The simultaneous rolling of alternate foils of the different components appears to be a very attractive method as it is both very simple and leads to a two-dimensional reinforced materials.

-
- 1) Union Carbide European Research Ass., Tech. Report No 23 (1968).
 - 2) Union Carbide European Research Ass., Tech. Report No 7 (1969).
 - 3) 7th Plansee Seminar - Tyrol (Austria) - June 1970.
 - 4) A. BERGHEZAN, COMPOSITES, vol. 3, No 5, Sept. 1972, p. 200.

7

TESTING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

GENEVA

G.A. Cooper, Chairman
J. Rexer, Co-Chairman

BOSTON

K. Hofer, Chairman
K. Prewo, Co-Chairman

KEY SPEAKER

T.T. Chiao

SELECTED PAPER

M.J. Owen

RAPPORTEUR

K. Kreider

CHAIRMAN'S SUMMARY REPORT

Session 7

by Dr. George A. Cooper
Manager, Mechanical Development Dept.
Institut CERAC S.A.
Centre Europeen de Recherches Atlas Copco
Chemin des Larges Pieces
CH-1024 Ecublens, Suisse

This session was one of the most important of the conference because in testing, one sees the meeting between theory and experiment, between prediction and reality. These two sides to the development of our knowledge are, of course, complementary, but it seems particularly apposite to comment on them at this time since we have seen considerable discussion of their relative merits in earlier sessions, and this discussion is very relevant to the approach one should have to the testing of composite materials, and, indeed to testing in general.

To make progress in our understanding of physical processes, we need a theory. The theory explains the relationship between phenomena and enables them to be compared. Some scientists would say that this is an end sufficient in itself, but surely the most powerful attribute of a theory is that it enables one to predict the behaviour of a system beforehand, without needing to make the test. Thus it is interesting and valuable to know why bodies with cracks and notches of different dimensions fail at different loads, but how much more valuable is it to use the theory to calculate safe working loads for ships, bridges and aircraft, and thereby to avoid the necessity to always build a prototype and subject it to test? Having said this, however, a conflict immediately becomes apparent, since a theory is only ever as good as the number of parameters it takes into account. There is always an element of risk in any extrapolation, insofar as phenomena which are unimportant and unnoticed in simple, small-scale tests may become dominant in the final application. The history of engineering is full of such interesting surprises; the subjects of fracture mechanics and fatigue in particular immediately spring to mind.

The essential value of testing is thus realized, since although it is always a goal to strive for, to have a theory which can be used to predict performance, one must always check the prediction against reality. The best tests are therefore those which are the closest to the application, and leave the least room for error; hence, for example, one sees complete airframes for advanced aircraft being subjected to combined thermal and mechanical fatigue stressing of the exact type they will encounter in their working lives, in the hope that even unsuspected failure mechanisms can be observed and counteracted in time. Such tests are, of course, extremely costly, and can only be undertaken for projects of great importance; we therefore come back again to the need for theory, to help us bridge the gap from cheap and simple tests on our basic materials to the accurate prediction of the properties of the engineering structure. I would therefore like to ask both experimentalists and theoreticians to consider the following propositions:

- 1) Development of theory has two aims: a) to understand and rationally compare observed phenomena, and b) to predict the performance of as-yet unbuilt devices. Of these, the latter is the most important.
- 2) Testing and observation has also two aims: a) to collect basic information, to be used in conjunction with theory for the prediction of performance, and b) to make phenomenological observations of behaviour, in order that the true physical processes underlying this behaviour are understood, and that the theory which is then developed is soundly based.

These ideas were also developed in a somewhat different form by our key speaker. He laid emphasis on the need for clarity in the formulation of the theory, and in particular for clarity in the use of mathematical terminology. He proposed that data for complex structures could be derived from a knowledge of the properties of a single lamina, a procedure which I would agree with for the prediction of elastic properties, but which seems beyond our present understanding for more complex properties such as fracture or fatigue. I would, however, echo his call for good quality control in the collection of the basic data, as it is of paramount importance to know the relation of the properties of the single test lamina to those of the equivalent element in the complex structure. In too many cases we have seen confusing results obtained due to the application of inaccurate test data to over-complex theory. It is essential to control and measure fibre content and orientation, and the porosity and degree of cure of the resin.

These points were even more strongly emphasized in Dr. Owen's paper, in which, apart from presenting several interesting anomalies between static and fatigue testing conditions, he examined the influence of various types of jointing procedure used in preparing his cylindrical test specimens. Here it was found that the exact

nature of the joint between successive layers of the chopped strand mat is very important to the fatigue process, and that failure to appreciate this point can lead to much confusion in the results.

I have little to add to the Rapporteur's most excellent review of the main bulk of the papers presented in this section. They covered a very wide range, both in terms of composite type - from metal-metal, through metal-ceramic to resin glass (including non-fibre systems and adhesive bonding), and also in terms of the type of testing used - measurement of elastic moduli, acoustic emission, fracture toughness and impact properties, and also fatigue.

From all this variety, it is difficult to draw any unifying conclusions, unless it be again to emphasize the value of obtaining high-quality data on well-characterized materials, and to note the number of "surprise" results which were obtained and subsequently understood, and which led to the discovery of hitherto unexpected mechanisms.

CHAIRMAN'S SUMMARY REPORT

Session 7

by K. E. Hofer, Jr.
Senior Research Engineer
Mechanics of Materials Division
IIT Research Institute
10 W. 35th Street
Chicago, Ill. 60616

INTRODUCTION

The excellent attendance at this session demonstrated the high interest retention in this basic area of composite materials. The papers in general evoked considerable comment and from the nature of these comments both fundamental and advanced problems are arising in the advanced composite design and application communities.

SESSION REPORT

The key speaker addressed the problems associated with the need for and application of orthotropic composite material property data. The discussion brought out the theoretical aspects of mechanical property data obtained for orthotropic composite material design and analysis. The talk was aimed at test engineers and illustrated the importance of test specimen design for the purpose of developing only the appropriate data. Questioning of the speaker relative to interpretation of various data from certain frequently-employed specimens revealed analytical problems in the treatment of those data. An observation, by this Chairman, is that the frequently misunderstood problems of testing analytically-simple geometries is even more severe than complicated analysis of experimentally-simple tests. I would also observe that the simpler the test procedure, the more reliable are the data; and specimens which are analytically-aseptic might often be impossible to test with any acceptable degree of

accuracy. It is imperative that not only analytical-experimental communication be established and maintained but that specimen fabrication variables, problems and solutions be treated with the direct contribution of fabrication engineers so as to produce material data of high quality and direct applicability to the problems now facing the advanced composite user industry.

The selected paper described a complex and ingenious method of fabricating and testing of cylindrical tubes. The scope of the questions and the breadth of the author's discussion of these questions indicates considerable interest in biaxial composite materials properties. In the Chairman's experience, the author's conclusion relevant to the importance of the second principal stress in failure of the composite is of particular merit. Many commonly-accepted failure theories based on maximum principal stresses are unacceptable for materials with a ratio of longitudinal strength to transverse strength of 20 or greater. The minimum principal stress is often, and possibly more often than not, the initiator of failure in composite materials.

The body of papers presented as a whole by the rapportner indicate a growing concern with notches, holes, and cracks. The fracture characteristics and failure mechanisms particularly in fatigue of composite materials are now being intensively investigated, particularly for graphite/epoxy composites where a "brittleness" problem is a major obstacle to their successful employment in advanced aerospace applications.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

It appears that future requirements on the reliability and fracture resistant characteristics of composite materials will spawn the next round of testing requirements, difficulties, and ultimately, solutions. The body of technical subjects thus generated will most likely form the central theme around which a later session at the 1976 ICCM on Testing of Composites will be based.